

Results

Sparingly Soluble Salt	Room temperature = 27°		Observed E.M.F. in mv	K _s
	Inside Solution			
	Cation Chamber (I)	Anion Chamber (III)		
	$a_{Ba^{+2}}$	$a_{SO_4^{2-}}$		
BaSO ₄	.001158	.00114	118.0	1.43×10^{-10}
	.001642	.00146	127.0	1.30×10^{-10}
		a_{CrO_4}		
BaCrO ₄	.001158	.001792	116.4	2.56×10^{-10}
	.004373	.001792	135.5	2.20×10^{-10}

The values of K_s calculated from the observed cell potentials are comparable to those obtained earlier by other methods³. In this method, the anion activity was not assumed to be the same as that of the cation even in the case of symmetrical electrolytes.

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Complexes of Dibenzoyl Sulphide with the Halides of Zinc, Cadmium and Mercury(II)

K. C. MALHOTRA* & J. K. PURI

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-14

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VERY little is known about the donor properties of dibenzoyl sulphide (Bz₂S₂) which has two donor sites namely, two carbonyl groups and one sulphur-sulphur bond. Some complexes of Bz₂S₂ with nitrogen bases are known¹ but the structural evidence is lacking. Recently some seven membered ring chelates of cobalt (II) and nickel (II) with Bz₂S₂ have been isolated and characterised² wherein both the carbonyl oxygen atoms have been shown to act as the donor groups. We now report the complexes of Bz₂S₂ with halides of zinc, cadmium and mercury (II) and an attempt has been made to elucidate their structures.

* Present address : Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University, Simla-1.

All these complexes were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of both the components in dry benzene when both the components went into the solution. The compounds were recovered by adding an inert solvent such as petroleum ether. The composition of these compounds has been determined by elemental analysis and is reported in Table 1. In the case of chlorides and bromides, zinc and cadmium halides form 1 : 1 complexes while mercury halides form 1 : 2 complexes with Bz₂S₂. The iodides do not form any compound suggesting the weaker acceptor strength of the iodides. Molar conductance values of the millimolar solutions in dimethylformamide is < 5.0 mhos which rules out their ionic give evidence of dissociation but when additional ligand is present to reduce dissociation, the results (Table 1) suggest that the complexes are monomeric.

Information on the structure of these complexes has been derived from i.r. spectral studies, especially in the lower region. Pure Bz₂S₂ shows one intense absorption band at 1670 cm⁻¹ and a weak band at 1750 cm⁻¹ assigned to $\nu(C=O)$; a weak band at 520 cm⁻¹ assigned to $\nu(S-S)$ and a sharp intense band at 670 cm⁻¹ assigned to $\nu(C-S)$ ^{3,4}. The band originally present at 1750 cm⁻¹ in Bz₂S₂ is shifted to 1655 cm⁻¹ and the one at 1670 cm⁻¹ is shifted to 1580 cm⁻¹ on complex formation showing that in preference to S-S group, coordination takes place at C=O group. There is no significant change in the frequencies of C-S and S-S stretching modes. If the lowering of the carbonyl stretching mode on complex formation is measure of the acceptor strength of the metal halides, then these may be arranged in the following order as :

Strong new bands (not present in the free ligands) are observed in these adducts. These new bands are insensitive to the change of halogen for a particular metal and are therefore assigned as i.r. active M-O stretching vibration modes. In the case of zinc halide complexes⁵, it is observed at 410 cm⁻¹, at ~ 360 cm⁻¹ in the case of cadmium halide complexes⁶ and at ~ 320 cm⁻¹ for mercury halide complexes⁷. Metal (II) oxygen modes usually occur below 500 cm⁻¹ in many complexes of metal (II) salts with oxygen donor⁸⁻¹⁰.

In the far i.r spectra of the zinc complexes, strong bands are also observed at 300 cm⁻¹ in the chloro and at 240 cm⁻¹ in the bromo complexes which may be assigned to $\nu(Zn-Cl)$ and $\nu(Z-Br)$ stretching modes respectively and are in fair agreement to Zn-Cl and Zn-Br stretching modes in many other Zn (II) complexes known to have tetrahedral environment about the zinc atom¹¹. The bands at 260 cm⁻¹ for chloro and at 220 cm⁻¹ for bromo derivatives of cadmium halide complexes found in the same range as reported in literature^{12,13} suggest a tetrahedral structure for these metal halides adducts. Polymeric structures with halogen bridging are unlikely because they are associated with metal-halogen stretching modes at lower frequencies¹⁴. In the case of mercury (II) halide complexes, strong bands at 320 cm⁻¹ for

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE ADDUCTS OF DIBENZOYL SULPHIDE AND HALIDES OF ZINC, CADMIUM AND MERCURY

Adduct	Colour	m.p. (°C)	Analysis				Molecular Weight		Molar conductance ²⁵ ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹
			% Found		% Calc.		Found	Calc.	
			Halogen	Sulphur	Halogen	Sulphur			
Bz ₂ S ₂ .ZnCl ₂	Pale yellow	144	17.56	16.02	17.28	15.62	406.8	410.3	1.8
Bz ₂ S ₂ .ZnBr ₂	Yellow	128	31.98	12.14	32.00	12.84	482.4	499.2	1.5
Bz ₂ S ₂ .CdCl ₂	Straw yellow	136	15.88	14.38	15.49	14.02	432.8	457.3	3.3
Bz ₂ S ₂ .CdBr ₂	Deep yellow	114	28.88	12.36	29.25	11.73	522.3	546.2	3.1
(Bz ₂ S ₂) ₂ .HgCl ₂	Brownish yellow	172	7.96	15.46	8.65	15.64	782.8	819.6	1.0
(Bz ₂ S ₂) ₂ .HgBr ₂	Brown	158	18.21	14.60	17.59	14.12	892.6	908.4	1.7

ν (Hg-Cl) and at 270 cm⁻¹ for ν (Hg-Br) stretching modes are observed which are in agreement with the reported values in literature¹⁵ and are assigned to terminal metal-halogen stretching mode. The stoichiometric composition of the compound suggests an octahedral structure for these adducts. Many compounds of mercury (II) are known to have an octahedral structure^{11,16}. The possibility of polymeric structures through halogen or the ligand bridges is ruled out as polymeric structures with halogen or ligand bridging are expected to give bands at lower frequencies than those observed.

Thermogravimetric analysis of all these adducts show that all these compounds dissociate into their components at their melting points and at around 150° benzoyl halide and polysulphides of the metals are formed.

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Studies of 2,4-Dihydroxyvalerophenone Oxime as an Analytical Reagent : Part II—Gravimetric Determination of Copper and Nickel

S. P. GUPTA, O. P. MALIK & JAI SINGH

Chemical Laboratories, D. N. College, Meerut

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IN our earlier communication¹, conductometric, potentiometric, micro-analysis, i.r. and n.m.r. studies of the metal complexes of 2,4-dihydroxyvalerophenone oxime (DHVOX) were reported. The reagent has now been successfully employed for the gravimetric determination of copper and nickel and their separation from a large number of other ions. It has been found that the precipitation of copper and nickel as its complex starts at pH 2.5 and 6.0 and is quantitative in the pH range 3.0 to 10.0 and 6.5 to 9.5 respectively. The precipitated complex has been found to possess the composition M(C₁₁H₁₄NO₃)₂.